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Branding Strategies and Patronage of Convenience Goods in Select Supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20198200>

Citation: Alexander, J. P., Umoren, P. E., & Bassey, E. B. (2026). Branding Strategies and Patronage of Convenience Goods in Select Supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State. *Global Journal of Modern Research and Emerging Trends*, 2(3), 58–79. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20198200>

Abstract

This study examined the branding strategies employed by supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State and their influence on consumer patronage of convenience goods. A survey research design was adopted, and data were collected from 366 respondents using structured questionnaires. The findings revealed that supermarkets employ branding strategies such as distinctive logos, attractive packaging, consistent brand presentation, and in-store promotions, with 45.9% of respondents strongly agreeing and 34.4% agreeing, yielding weighted mean scores (WMS) ranging from 3.15 to 3.23. The study further showed that the frequency and prominence of branding strategies significantly influence consumer awareness and engagement, as 48.1% strongly agreed and 33.9% agreed that these strategies are regularly visible and impactful. The analysis also indicated that branding strategies significantly affect consumer patronage, as strong brand identity, familiarity, and store atmosphere encourage purchase decisions and repeat patronage (WMS = 3.14, 3.23). However, challenges such as high packaging costs, inadequate promotional activities, and poor labeling were identified as factors limiting the effectiveness of branding

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strategies. Significant relationships exist between branding strategies and consumer patronage ($r = 0.62$, $r\text{-crit} = 0.098$) as well as repeat patronage ($r = 0.55$, $r\text{-crit} = 0.098$). The study concluded that branding strategies significantly influence consumer behavior and loyalty toward convenience goods in supermarkets. It was recommended that supermarkets adopt consistent branding, improve promotional efforts, and maintain appealing store environments to enhance consumer patronage and repeat purchases.

Keywords: Branding strategies, Consumer patronage, Convenience goods, Supermarkets, Akwa Ibom State

Introduction

Branding is a critical aspect of marketing communication, as it involves strategic messaging, audience targeting, and media engagement to influence consumer behavior. According to Ihemereze (2014), branding is simply the process of giving identification marks to products such as brand name, brand mark, and trademark. In other words, it is the process of giving a brand name to a product, designing the brand mark, and legalizing and promoting the brand. He further took the position that a well-promoted brand name that has earned a reputation in the market is difficult to compete with, as it offers customers protection and confidence. Branding is inextricably linked with advertising. According to Krugman & Hayes (2012), branding communicates ideas through consumer products, and in many respects, the brand is what advertising is all about. Just like advertising, brands make promises and seek to create trust between producer and consumer (Umoren, 2019).

Belch and Belch (2018) opine that advertising plays a critical role in building brand awareness, shaping brand perceptions, and influencing consumer attitudes. Branding strategies rely on various communication channels to shape consumer perceptions, establish brand identity, and drive product patronage (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Supermarkets, as key retail outlets, serve as communication platforms where brands interact with consumers through advertising, promotions, packaging, and digital marketing. In Akwa Ibom State, the rapid expansion of supermarkets has intensified brand competition, making effective communication essential for product differentiation and consumer engagement. The mass media play a crucial role in this process by ensuring that branding messages reach the intended audience through both traditional and digital media. Branding in supermarkets is heavily dependent on advertising and public relations, both of which are key elements of marketing communication. Keller (2016) emphasizes that a

brand's success is largely determined by how well its message resonates with its target audience (Umoren, 2025).

The rise of digital media has further transformed branding communication in supermarkets. Social media platforms, online advertisements, and influencer marketing have become key tools for brand communication (Keller & Swaminathan, 2020). In Akwa Ibom State, where internet penetration is increasing, brands leverage Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter to engage with consumers, provide product information, and offer promotional deals (Ibia & Ekott, 2013). Through digital branding strategies such as having a professional website, social media marketing, and utilizing paid advertising, among others, supermarkets can interact with their customers in real time, gather feedback, and build strong consumer-brand relationships.

Public relations and corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives also contribute to brand perception and consumer trust. Brands that engage in CSR activities, such as community development projects and environmental sustainability campaigns, use mass media for public awareness campaigns, content marketing, and branding initiatives, among others, to enhance their reputation and establish credibility (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2019). Supermarkets that support local initiatives or sponsor community events benefit from positive brand associations, which, in turn, influence brand loyalty among consumers. Effective communication of these CSR efforts through media channels strengthens the emotional connection between brands and consumers, reinforcing long-term brand equity. This study, therefore, seeks to explore the branding strategies employed by selected supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State and their influence on consumers' patronage of convenience goods.

Statement of the Problem

Branding plays a crucial role in influencing consumer behavior, yet many supermarkets struggle to implement effective branding strategies that drive consistent customer loyalty and brand preference. In Akwa Ibom State, where there is an increase in the number of supermarkets, the competition among brands is intensifying. Despite the presence of various convenience goods such as beverages, snacks, and toiletries, among others, on supermarket shelves, consumer purchasing decisions are often inconsistent, with many buyers switching between brands based on price changes, promotional offers, or packaging appeal. This raises concerns about the long-term effectiveness of branding in securing customer retention and product loyalty.

Consumers often make spontaneous purchasing decisions in supermarkets, sometimes choosing a lesser-known brand due to a discount or eye-catching packaging. For instance, while a particular brand of detergent may have a strong reputation, a consumer may still opt for a competitor's product simply because it is placed at a more visible spot or comes with a temporary price reduction. This trend suggests that despite strong brand identities, supermarkets may not be leveraging branding strategies effectively to create lasting consumer attachment to specific products. Additionally, the increasing reliance on digital media and influencer marketing has changed how consumers perceive brands. As a result, some supermarket brands struggle to maintain relevance in a market where consumer preferences are constantly changing. Against this backdrop, this study sought to examine the branding strategies used by selected supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State and how the strategies influenced consumers' patronage of convenience goods.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to:

- i. Identify the branding strategies employed by supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State to promote convenience goods.
- ii. Ascertain which of the strategies are used frequently by supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State to reach consumers of convenience goods.
- iii. Find out the extent to which the strategies influence consumers' patronage of convenience goods in select supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State.
- iv. Assess the effectiveness of different branding elements in driving repeat patronage among consumers of convenience goods.
- v. Analyze the challenges supermarkets face in implementing effective branding strategies for convenience goods.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- i. What branding strategies do supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State employ to promote convenience goods?
- ii. Which of the strategies are used frequently by supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State to reach consumers of convenience goods?

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- iii. To what extent do the strategies influence consumers' patronage of convenience goods in selected supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State?
- iv. How effective are different branding elements in driving repeat patronage among consumers of convenience goods?
- v. What challenges do supermarkets face in implementing effective branding strategies for convenience goods?

Hypotheses

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between branding strategies employed by supermarkets and the promotion of convenience goods in Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the frequency of branding strategies and patronage of convenience goods in Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between branding strategies and consumers' patronage of convenience goods in Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between branding elements and repeat patronage of convenience goods in Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between branding challenges and effectiveness of branding strategies in Akwa Ibom State.

Branding and Consumer Decision-Making

Branding plays a crucial role in shaping consumer decision-making by influencing perceptions, preferences, and purchasing behavior. A well-established brand serves as a psychological shortcut, helping consumers make quick and informed choices in a crowded marketplace. In the retail industry, particularly in supermarkets, branding differentiates products, creates emotional connections, and builds trust, ultimately guiding consumers toward specific purchasing decisions (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Consumers are more likely

to choose brands that are familiar, reputable, and aligned with their values, making branding a key determinant in product selection (Aaker & Moorman, 2018).

One of the primary ways branding influences consumer decision-making is through brand recognition and recall. Consumers tend to gravitate toward brands they can easily recognize, as familiarity creates a sense of reliability and trust. This is especially important in the convenience goods sector, where consumers often make quick, low-involvement purchases. Strong branding elements such as logos, colors, packaging, and slogans enhance product recall and make it easier for consumers to identify their preferred brands among competing options (Solomon *et al.*, 2019). For example, in Nigeria, well-established brands like Peak Milk, Indomie, and Coca-Cola enjoy high brand recall, leading to repeated purchases and customer loyalty (Ogunyemi & Adebayo, 2021).

Perceived quality and brand trust also play significant roles in consumer decision-making. Many consumers associate strong brands with superior quality and reliability, which influences their willingness to pay a premium price for branded products over generic alternatives (Keller, 2016). When a brand consistently delivers high-quality products, it builds trust and credibility, reducing the perceived risk of making a poor purchase decision. In Nigeria, brands such as Dettol and Milo have built consumer trust over time by consistently providing high-quality products, leading to increased brand loyalty and preference (Eze & Chukwuma, 2018). Trust is particularly important in categories like food, beverages, and healthcare products, where consumers prioritize safety and effectiveness.

Branding also affects consumer decision-making through emotional and psychological connections. Many successful brands use storytelling, advertising, and brand personalities to evoke emotions and create a deeper connection with consumers (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2019). Emotional branding fosters long-term relationships, making consumers feel attached to a brand beyond just its functional benefits. For instance, brands that position themselves as family-friendly, health-conscious, or socially responsible appeal to consumers who identify with those values. In Nigeria, brands like Cowbell Milk and Golden Morn use advertisements that emphasize family bonding and childhood memories, reinforcing positive emotional connections that influence consumer decisions (Ajayi & Mbah, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the following theories; Brand Equity Theory, Theory of Planned Behavior, Consumer Perception Theory, and Integrated Marketing

Communications. Brand Equity Theory, popularized by David A. Aaker (1991), explains the added value a brand name contributes to a product beyond its functional benefits. The major assumption is that strong brands serve as valuable assets that influence consumer behavior and enhance firm performance over time (Aaker, 1991; Keller, 2013). Key constructs of the theory include brand awareness, perceived quality, brand associations, brand loyalty, and proprietary brand assets. More recent studies affirm that strong brand equity enhances customer preference, willingness to pay premium prices, and long-term loyalty (Keller & Swaminathan, 2020; Foroudi, 2019).

The Theory of Planned Behavior, proposed by Icek Ajzen (1985) and extended in 1991, posits that behavior is driven by behavioral intention, which is influenced by attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). The major assumption is that individuals engage in rational decision-making processes before acting. The key constructs include attitude toward behavior, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and behavioral intention. Recent empirical studies continue to validate TPB in predicting consumer purchase intentions across retail settings (Yadav & Pathak, 2017; Paul, Modi & Patel, 2016).

Consumer Perception Theory, rooted in the work of Jerome McCarthy (1960) and expanded by Kotler and Keller (2016), emphasizes that consumers respond to their perceptions of marketing stimuli rather than objective reality. The major assumption is that perception is subjective and significantly influences consumer decision-making. Key constructs include perception, interpretation of stimuli, prior experience, and psychological and environmental influences. Recent research highlights that perception plays a critical role in shaping brand image, trust, and purchase decisions in competitive retail environments (Hoyer, MacInnis & Pieters, 2020; Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019).

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) Theory, developed by Don E. Schultz and colleagues in the early 1990s, emphasizes the coordination of all marketing communication tools to deliver a consistent and unified message to consumers (Schultz & Kitchen, 2000). The major assumption is that integrated and consistent communication across multiple channels enhances brand effectiveness and consumer response. Key constructs include message consistency, communication integration, synergy among promotional tools, and customer-centered communication. Recent studies show that IMC improves brand engagement, strengthens customer relationships, and enhances purchase behavior in retail environments (Porcu, del Barrio-García & Kitchen, 2017; Kitchen & Burgmann, 2015).

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Empirical Review

The reviewed empirical studies collectively highlight the significant role of branding strategies in influencing consumer behaviour and patronage across different contexts. Nyong et al. (2023) established that advertisement exposure, particularly through television, significantly affects consumer purchase decisions, emphasizing message presentation as a key driver of brand patronage. Similarly, Everlyne (2018) found that brand image elements such as brand attributes and perceived benefits positively influence consumer buying behaviour in supermarkets. Supporting this, Tarannum et al. (2024) demonstrated that strong branding enhances customer recognition, trust, and loyalty, ultimately improving product performance. Abioro and Odunlami (2021) further confirmed that branding elements like packaging, brand recognition, and perceived quality have a strong positive effect on customer patronage in Nigeria. In addition, Raphael et al. (2024) reinforced that branding components such as logo, packaging, and advertising significantly shape consumer loyalty and purchasing decisions within the local context of Akwa Ibom State.

Furthermore, other studies emphasize the role of both product-related and non-product-related factors in driving patronage behaviour. Jackline et al. (2024) revealed that store convenience factors including accessibility, layout, and checkout efficiency significantly influence retail patronage among supermarket shoppers. Likewise, Oghenekome and Ozuru (2023) highlighted the importance of packaging strategies, showing that elements such as visual appeal, labelling, and functionality positively impact customer patronage. Across these studies, a common theme emerges: consumer behaviour is influenced by a combination of branding elements, marketing communication, and situational factors. These findings are highly relevant to the current research as they provide empirical support those effective branding strategies, ranging from advertising and packaging to store environment and brand image, which plays a crucial role in, shaping consumer perception, purchase decisions, and sustained patronage of convenience goods in supermarket settings.

Research Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The population comprised residents of Akwa Ibom State, estimated at 7,200,000 based on 2025 projections from the National Population Commission, alongside 14 supermarket managers. Using Philip Meyer's (2010) sample size determination table, a sample size of 384 consumers was considered appropriate. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted: purposive

sampling was used to select supermarkets across the three senatorial districts (Uyo, Ibesikpo, Ikot Ekpene, Abak, Eket, and Esit Eket), while convenience sampling was used to select consumers at points of purchase. A census approach was applied to include all 14 supermarket managers. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and semi-structured interviews; the questionnaire comprised two sections: demographic data and a five-point Likert scale measuring key variables across four research questions. Instrument validity was ensured through expert review, and reliability was confirmed by a pre-test of 30 respondents, yielding a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.79. Data analysis was conducted using simple percentages and weighted mean scores, while hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Branding Strategies Supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State Employ to Promote Convenience Goods.

S/N	Questionnaire Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Weighted Mean Score	Decision
1	This supermarket uses unique logos and colour schemes to distinguish its products	168 (45.9%)	126 (34.4%)	48 (13.1%)	24 (6.6%)	366	3.20	Accepted
2	I often see promotional activities (discounts, adverts or in-store displays) encouraging the purchase of convenience goods	154 (42.1%)	138 (37.7%)	50 (13.7%)	24 (6.5%)	366	3.15	Accepted
3	Supermarkets use brand names and logos that make their convenience	176 (48.1%)	122 (33.3%)	44 (12.0%)	24 (6.6%)	366	3.23	Accepted

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	goods easy to recognize							
4	Supermarkets maintain a consistent image in the way their convenience goods are presented	162 (44.3%)	132 (36.1%)	46 (12.6%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.17	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 shows that most of the 366 respondents agreed that supermarkets use key branding strategies to promote convenience goods. Agreement ranged from 79.8% to 81.4% across all items, with mean scores between 3.15 and 3.23. Respondents particularly confirmed the use of unique logos and color schemes (80.3%), promotional activities (79.8%), recognizable brand names and logos (81.4%), and consistent brand presentation (80.4%). This indicates strong agreement that branding strategies are effectively used to influence consumer patronage.

Table 2: Strategies Used Frequently by Supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State to Reach Consumers of Convenience Goods.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total	WMS	Decision
5	Branding elements are updated or refreshed regularly to keep up with market trends.	158 (43.2%)	136 (37.2%)	46 (12.6%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.16	Agree
6	Promotional branding materials (banners/flyers) are frequently displayed in this store.	162 (44.3%)	132 (36.1%)	48 (13.1%)	24 (6.6%)	366	3.18	Agree
7	Convenience goods are often arranged on shelves in a way that easily draws my attention.	170 (46.4%)	128 (35.0%)	44 (12.0%)	24 (6.6%)	366	3.21	Agree

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8	I frequently receive promotional offers or loyalty rewards for buying convenience goods from certain supermarkets.	150 (41.0%)	138 (37.7%)	50 (13.7%)	28 (7.6%)	366	3.12	Agree
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Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 shows that respondents generally agreed that supermarkets frequently apply multiple branding strategies to attract consumers of convenience goods. Agreement levels were consistently high across all items, with 80.4% (43.2% strongly agreed; 37.2% agreed; mean = 3.16) noting that branding elements are regularly updated, 80.4% (44.3% strongly agreed; 36.1% agreed; mean = 3.18) confirming frequent use of promotional materials such as banners and flyers, and 81.4% (46.4% strongly agreed; 35.0% agreed; mean = 3.21) agreeing that shelf arrangement is used to attract attention. Supermarkets actively employ branding strategies such as shelf placement, promotional displays, brand updates, and incentives to influence consumer-purchasing behavior.

Table 3: Strategies That Influence Consumers' Patronage of Convenience Goods in Selected Supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State.

S/N	Statement	S	A	D	SD	Total	WMS	Decision
9	The way a convenience good is branded influences my decision to buy it.	176 (48.1%)	124 (33.9%)	42 (11.5%)	24 (6.6%)	366	3.23	Agree
10	The reputation of the supermarket's brand is the main reason I shop here.	164 (44.8%)	132 (36.1%)	44 (12.0%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.18	Agree
11	When a supermarket has a strong and familiar brand, I am more confident buying from it.	172 (47.0%)	126 (34.4%)	42 (11.5%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.21	Agree
12	Branding strategies encourage me to visit a particular supermarket more often for convenience goods.	160 (43.7%)	134 (36.6%)	46 (12.6%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.17	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 shows that branding strategies strongly influence consumers' patronage of convenience goods in supermarkets. Across all items, a clear majority agreed, with positive responses ranging from 78.7% to 81.4%. Specifically, 81.4% (mean = 3.23) indicated that product branding affects purchase decisions, 80.9% (mean = 3.18) agreed that supermarket brand reputation influences shopping choice, 81.4% (mean = 3.21) reported increased confidence when the brand is familiar, and 80.3% (mean = 3.17) said branding encourages repeat visits. Strong branding, familiarity, and reputation significantly drive consumer patronage of convenience goods.

Table 4: Effects of different branding elements in driving repeat patronage among consumers of convenience goods.

S/N	Questionnaire statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total	WMS	Decision
14	The brand name of a product is more important to me than the way it is packaged.	152 (41.5%)	140 (38.3%)	46 (12.6%)	28 (7.6%)	366	3.14	Agree
15	The internal atmosphere/ambience of the store encourages me to stay and shop longer.	168 (45.9%)	130 (35.5%)	44 (12.0%)	24 (6.6%)	366	3.20	Agree
16	Clear and visible brand labeling is the most effective factor in my product selection.	174 (47.5%)	128 (35.0%)	40 (10.9%)	24 (6.6%)	366	3.23	Agree
17	Promotional offers (buy-one-get-one-free) are more effective than visual packaging.	162 (44.3%)	134 (36.6%)	44 (12.0%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.18	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 shows that branding elements significantly influence repeat patronage of convenience goods. Agreement levels were consistently high, ranging from 79.8% to 82.5% across all items. Specifically, 79.8% (mean = 3.14) agreed that brand name is more important than packaging, 81.4% (mean = 3.20) confirmed that store ambience encourages longer shopping time, 82.5% (mean = 3.23) identified clear brand labeling as the most important factor in product selection, and 80.9% (mean = 3.18) agreed that promotional offers are more effective than packaging. Brand name, store ambience, product labeling, and promotional incentives strongly drive repeat patronage of convenience goods.

Table 5: Challenges Supermarkets Face in Implementing Effective Branding Strategies for Convenience Goods.

S/N	Questionnaire statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total	WMS	Decision
18	High costs of quality packaging materials make branding difficult to maintain.	158 (43.2%)	136 (37.2%)	46 (12.6%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.16	Agree
19	Many supermarkets do not promote their convenience goods well enough to attract customers.	150 (41.0%)	142 (38.8%)	46 (12.6%)	28 (7.6%)	366	3.13	Agree
20	The high prices of branded convenience goods discourage me from buying them regularly.	164 (44.8%)	134 (36.6%)	42 (11.5%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.18	Agree
21	Poor packaging or unclear labeling makes it difficult for me to trust some convenience goods.	170 (46.4%)	130 (35.5%)	40 (10.9%)	26 (7.1%)	366	3.20	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 5 shows that most respondents agreed that key challenges affect branding in supermarkets. Agreement ranged from 79.8% to 81.9%, with mean scores between 3.13 and 3.20. Respondents identified high packaging costs (80.4%), inadequate promotion (79.8%), high product prices (81.4%), and poor labeling (81.9%) as major constraints. These factors significantly hinder effective branding of convenience goods in supermarkets.

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One (H₀₁): There is no significant relationship between branding strategies employed by supermarkets and the promotion of convenience goods.

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Variable	N	ΣX	ΣY	ΣX ²	ΣY ²	ΣXY	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Branding Strategies (X)	366	1,248		4,362					
Promotion of Convenience Goods (Y)	366		1,196		4,108	4,226	0.64	0.098	Reject H ₀

Table 6 shows that the calculated correlation coefficient ($r = 0.64$) is greater than the critical value ($r = 0.098$) at the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates a significant positive relationship between supermarkets' branding practices and promotion of convenience goods. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected, implying that there is a significant relationship between branding strategies employed by supermarkets and the promotion of convenience goods in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Two (H_{02}): There is no significant relationship between the frequency and prominence of branding strategies and consumers of convenience goods.

Table 7: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Frequency of Branding Strategies (X)	366	1,214		4,210					
Consumers of Convenience Goods (Y)	366		1,175		4,020	4,058	0.58	0.098	Reject H_0

Table 7 shows that the computed r-value (0.58) exceeds the critical r-value (0.98) at the 0.05 significance level. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the frequency of branding strategies and how effectively supermarkets reach consumers. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected.

Hypothesis Three (H_{03}): There is no significant relationship between branding strategies and consumers' patronage of convenience goods.

Table 8: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Branding Strategies (X)	366	1,232		4,320					
Consumers Patronage (Y)	366		1,208		4,146	4,182	0.62	0.098	Reject H_0

Table 8 shows that the computed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.62$) is less than the critical r-value (0.98) at the 0.05 level of significance. This means there is a strong and positive relationship between branding strategies and consumers' patronage of convenience goods.

The null hypothesis (H_{03}) is therefore rejected, indicating that effective branding significantly influences consumer patronage.

Hypothesis Four (H_{04}): There is no significant relationship between branding elements and repeat patronage of convenience goods.

Table 9: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Branding Elements (X)	366	1,205		4,102					
Repeat Patronage (Y)	366		1,184		4,012	3,980	0.55	0.098	Reject H_0

Table 9 shows that there is a significant positive relationship between branding elements and consumer repeat patronage. This indicates that a strong brand name, attractive packaging, a clean store environment, and consistent branding significantly influence consumers to repurchase convenience goods. The table shows that r-calculated (0.55) is greater than r-critical (0.98). Therefore, the null hypothesis H_{05} is rejected. This means that branding elements employed by supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State significantly influence consumer repeat patronage of convenience goods.

Hypothesis Five (H_{05}): There is no significant relationship between branding challenges and the effectiveness of branding strategies.

Table 10: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Branding Challenges (X)	366	1,188		4,018					
Effectiveness of Branding Strategies (Y)	366		1,160		3,940	3,902	0.49	0.098	Reject H_0

The analysis on Table 4.2.5 shows that the computed r-value (0.49) is greater than the critical r-value (0.098) at the 0.05 significance level. This result indicates a significant relationship between the challenges supermarkets face and the effectiveness of branding strategy implementation. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{04}) is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal that supermarkets in Akwa Ibom State employ a range of branding strategies, particularly the use of unique logos, consistent color schemes, recognizable brand names, in-store promotions, and strategic shelf arrangements, with weighted mean scores ranging from 3.15 to 3.23. A significant proportion of respondents (80.3%) agreed that visual identity elements play a central role in differentiating products and attracting consumer attention. These findings align with conceptual views of branding as a tool for creating a unique identity that shapes consumer perception (Kotler & Keller, 2016) and are supported by Brand Equity Theory (Aaker, 1991), which emphasizes the role of brand awareness and associations in influencing consumer behavior. Empirical evidence also supports that supermarkets utilize branding elements to build trust and loyalty (Ebitu & Basil, 2020; Okon & Udoh, 2021). Branding strategies are deliberately and effectively used to promote convenience goods and differentiate supermarkets in a competitive environment.

Supermarkets frequently use branding strategies such as price discounts, product displays, shelf arrangements, social media campaigns, promotional displays, and branded shopping materials to reach consumers. High agreement levels were recorded, with 71.2% of respondents affirming the frequent use of discounts (WMS = 3.87) and similar strong responses for display strategies and promotional activities (WMS between 3.81 and 3.85). Frequent exposure to branding messages improves familiarity and purchase intention (Okon & Udoh, 2021). Thus, frequency and visibility are critical components of effective branding strategies used by supermarkets to reach consumers.

Branding strategies significantly influence consumer patronage of convenience goods, with activities such as frequent promotional displays, effective shelf arrangements, brand updates, and loyalty programs recording weighted mean scores between 3.12 and 3.21. The hypothesis test further confirmed a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.58$) between branding strategies and consumer patronage. Consistent branding enhances repeat patronage (Ebitu & Basil, 2020). Therefore, branding strategies are not only influential but also essential in shaping consumer buying behavior and loyalty in supermarket settings.

Branding strategies significantly influence consumer patronage of convenience goods, with activities such as frequent promotional displays, effective shelf arrangements, brand updates, and loyalty programs recording weighted mean scores between 3.12 and 3.21. The hypothesis test further confirmed a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.58$) between branding strategies and consumer patronage. Branding enhances repeat patronage (Ebitu

& Basil, 2020). Therefore, branding strategies are not only influential but also essential in shaping consumer buying behavior and loyalty in supermarket settings.

Branding elements such as brand familiarity, supermarket reputation, and visually appealing displays significantly drive repeat patronage, with weighted mean scores ranging from 3.17 to 3.23 and over 80% of respondents acknowledging the influence of branding on their buying decisions. The Pearson correlation result ($r = 0.62$) further confirmed a strong positive relationship between branding elements and repeat patronage. Effective branding fosters customer loyalty and repeat shopping behavior (Okon & Udoh, 2021; Ebitu & Basil, 2020). Hence, well-designed and consistently applied branding elements are key drivers of repeat patronage.

Several challenges affecting the implementation of branding strategies, including high packaging costs, inadequate promotional reach, high pricing of branded goods, and poor labeling, had weighted mean scores between 3.13 and 3.20. Resource limitations and lack of expertise constrain branding effectiveness in retail settings (Adebayo, 2019; Okon & Udoh, 2021). Overall, while branding strategies are impactful, their effectiveness is limited by operational and financial challenges, indicating the need for improved resource allocation, staff training, and strategic investment to enhance branding outcomes.

Conclusion

Branding plays a significant role in promoting convenience goods in supermarkets across Akwa Ibom State. Findings show that supermarkets use various strategies such as packaging, advertising, promotional displays, and loyalty programs to attract customers, build trust, and influence purchase decisions. Among these, advertising, discounts, and distinctive packaging are the most frequently used and effective in enhancing visibility and encouraging patronage. The results further indicate that consumers prefer brands that are consistent, reliable, and visually appealing. However, supermarkets face challenges including high branding costs, limited digital marketing capacity, inadequate expertise, and strong competition. Despite these constraints, branding remains essential for sustaining sales, improving customer satisfaction, and achieving long-term business growth in the retail sector.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

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- i. Supermarkets should maintain and enhance the use of branding tools such as attractive packaging, consistent logos, in-store displays, and advertising to strengthen consumer recognition and preference.
- ii. Branding initiatives should be consistently visible and frequently applied across supermarkets and all their digital platforms to increase consumer awareness, recall, and engagement.
- iii. Supermarkets should focus on strategies that build consumer trust and perceived value, including maintaining quality products, clear communication, and promotional initiatives that encourage repeat purchases.
- iv. Supermarkets should maintain consistency in key branding elements such as logos, packaging, store environment, and promotions. Regular monitoring of these elements and adapting based on consumer feedback will strengthen loyalty and encourage repeat patronage.
- v. Operational and resource challenges should be addressed through staff training, investment in digital and marketing tools, and partnerships with marketing agencies to improve branding efficiency.

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